

EFFECTIVE TEACHING STRATEGIES FOR CHILDREN WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES IN INCLUSIVE SETTING

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1. Abstract :

Inclusivity is defined as fostering a collaborative learning environment that transcend student diversity. To support this teacher, employ diverse pedagogical strategies. This study aims to identify effective teaching approaches that promote inclusivity, like especially enhancing the academic performance of students with learning disabilities. Data collection and analysis was done through qualitative research methods. The findings indicate that, while various individual strategies are beneficial and integrated, and integrative pedological approach groups more effective than in single teaching strategy.

Keywords:

learning disability, pedagogical learning methods, qualitative research, inclusive classroom

2. INTRUCTION:

2.1. CONCEPT OF LEARNING DISABILITY:

According to the RPWD Act, 2016, “Specific Learning Disability” is one of the most common impairments of all. A learning disability is a diverse condition where the children face some problems in their information processing system that may hinder the broad area of their comprehending, speaking, reading, writing, and calculation. Children with learning disabilities are often able to excel in many fields other than their specific learning areas. A person with dyslexia, dysgraphia, slow learners, minimal brain damage or educational handicaps can come under these types of impairment (santhanam, Babu, & Sugandhi, 2014). Learning disabilities can not only affect the academic area but also hinder the individual’s day-to-day life, socialization and interpersonal relationships. Learning disabilities can be divided into two major types, such as “Major Types” and “Other Types”.

A. Major types

1. Dyscalculia- This is a neurological condition where children face various difficulties in apprehending different types of mathematics, numbers, and symbols.
2. Dysgraphia- This is another common type of learning disability that affects a person’s fine motor skills, basically their writing ability.
3. Dyslexia- In this condition children are unable to process their language skills which affect their reading skills. They are unable to understand spelling and alphabets.

B. Other types

1. Auditory processing disorder- Auditory processing disorder is a condition in which our brain is unable to meaningfully analyse and interpret the different types of sound that we receive through our ears despite normal hearing.
2. Visual processing disorder- A person with this kind of disorder is unable to understand and analyse different types of information. Even they face difficulty in drawing or copying.
3. Nonverbal learning disorder- A disorder that is usually characterised by the incapability to apprehend the nonverbal cues like facial expression or body language.
4. Language processing disorder- This is a specific type of learning disability where an individual faces trouble making the meaning of a sound that forms a word, sentence, and stories.

2.2. CONCEPT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION :

Inclusive education is an education system in which ordinary children and especially abled children are educated together. In this education system, spatially able children are not separated from ordinary children in any way, regardless of their differences or disabilities. The main goal of this education system is that no child is deprived of any opportunity or development in any way. Inclusive schools stand on the principle that all students in the society should learn together (Sebba & Sachdev, 1997). Inclusive education is an education system in which children with special needs are given social recognition like other children, and their education is based on their individual and specific needs (Norwich,1999).

Children with specific learning disabilities encounter academic hurdles in their life. The biggest problem among them is when they are trained together with normal children in the same classroom. Not only the children but also teachers face these problems. The main concern of every teacher is that how and in what way they will teach normal and especially able children together in the same classroom.

The main aim of teachers will be to use methods that will make learning more accessible and easier for the children with learning disabilities. Special educators are trained to conduct different types of learning strategies in the classroom to help the children with learning disabilities.

2.3.CONCEPT OF LEARNING STRATEGIES:

Approximately 10% of the population are affected by the specific learning disability. (R. Suri & Bhardwaj, 2024) so, the teachers have to adopt various techniques to educate these children. In case teachers will use the different learning strategies in a single or in an integrated way, then it is easier to acquire the knowledge for the children with learning disabilities in an inclusive classroom setting. Some of the learning strategies that can be used in an inclusive classroom settings are listed below.

1.MULTISENSORY INSTRUCTIONS- Multi-sensory instruction is a method through which children are able to acquire knowledge through the use of their multiple senses (visual, auditory, kinaesthetic and tactile), which helps to enhance their memory and learning. For example, a teacher might use visual aids and verbal instructions to teach the concept of “levels of atmosphere” that will help the students with learning disability to gain the information in an easier way.

2.DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION- Differentiated instruction is a holistic approach or framework that can be used by a teacher to accommodate and acknowledge various kind of content, process and product together to meet diverse need and interest of the students. For example, a teacher might provide flipped classroom and scaffold techniques to help the children with disabilities to assess and comprehend the content effortlessly.

3.INDIVIDUALISED EDUCATON PLAN- This strategy is use to identify the strength and weakness of each individual. This is focusing on the specific need of the individual and its main aim is to enhance the educational goal of the students. For example, to improve the spelling of a student with learning disability teachers organize an extra class.

4.CO-OPERATIVE LEARNING APPROACH- In co-operative learning, teachers organize students into small and diverse ability groups where students empower themselves by sharing their knowledge, skills, and working towards common goals. For example, in think-pair share methods students firstly think individually about a topic then discuss it with their partner.

5.EXPLISIT INSTRUCTION- In these strategies, teachers are used deductive methods where they break down the complex content into a manageable form. The main goal of these strategies is to provide a systematic and structured content to the students to understand the concept in an easier way. For example, teacher use this technique to teach a child with dyslexia by breaking down a paragraph into a small sentence, words, phonic.

6.POSITIVE BEHAVIOUR SUPPORT- positive behaviour support is a person-centred strategy to understand the negative behaviour of the children that can create hindrance and restrain challenging behaviour by providing a supportive environment. Positive reinforcement is an example of this technique. For example, after correcting each spelling teacher will provide feedback to the child.

7.ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGY- Teachers using as assistive device like in a learning procedure to remove educational barrier for children with learning disabilities. This type of device is able to meet the specific and unique needs of every child. For example, teacher may use text- to- speech, audio-books or screen readers for students with dyslexia.

8.CONSTRUCTIVISM APPROACH- Constructivism approach help the child to build their own knowledge and ideas though real-life experience and social in inclusive classrooms, educators frequently employ constructivist approach such as peer tutoring, scaffolding, problem solving to support diverse learners. For example, by using peer tutoring methods, students are assigned into

3 groups, each group is presented one particular unit and teach the other groups on supervision of the teacher.

Selecting and utilizing the most effective teaching techniques facilitate the learning process of the children with disabilities. This is basically a very important task for the teachers as no one with learning disability responds similarly because they are not affected by a same problem so, careful monitoring and case study can help the teacher to select the techniques that are useful for them. The main aim of this study is to identify the teaching strategies that are effective for children with learning disabilities in inclusive settings.

3.REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

A. CONSTRUCTIVISM:

According to the constructivism approach to learning, students are actively participating in the learning process and construct their own knowledge through their previous experiences. Children vigorously form their understanding and knowledge about the world by their prior experience and reflecting on those experiences (Bereiter, 1994). Constructivism-based practice can affect cognitive development and focuses on making learning much more meaningful through interaction among peers, family, and teachers (Al-Shammari, Faulkner, & Chris, 2019).

B. COOPERATIVE:

A cooperative learning strategy is a student-centered approach in which a group of students is responsible for their own learning by facilitating each other's knowledge. A study done by E. Salvin (1996) elucidates that the academic performance and level of achievement may improve through cooperative learning strategies. Cooperative learning strategies develop students' attitudes toward learning and among themselves, fostering the learning environment (Singay, 2029).

C. POSITIVE BEHAVIOR SUPPORT:

The positive supported strategies are used by the teachers to enhance the environment of the classroom that facilitates the learning process. Rinaldi, Averill, & Orla (2011) demonstrate research that suggested positive behaviour support is the best tool used by the teachers to achieve the positive school environment. Positive behaviour support techniques are an effective approach that enhances academic performance and promotes adjustment by reducing problems for students with high-risk behaviours (Bradshaw, Waasdorp, & Leaf, 2012).

D. DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONS:

Modifying instructional strategies that facilitate specific needs of the individual is called differentiated instruction. With the help of differentiated instructions, teachers can create a high-level curriculum that recognizes the diversity of the children and helps to improve and achieve academic success by addressing their specific needs (Tomlinson, 2001). Another research study done by Adeniran et al. (2025) revealed that differentiated instructions enhance the learner's academic performance more than the other traditional learning approach by promoting equity.

E. ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGY:

Assistive technology use in learning is a tool that provides devices, software, and equipment to support the students with disabilities to access education and simplify their academic performance. By providing assistive devices to the students with disabilities, they are able to overcome various hindrances and succeed in receiving an education and achieving their academic performance in an inclusive classroom (Lodhi & Dr. Singh, 2024). Research done by Marino et al. (2014) demonstrated that the students with dyslexia may improve their academic performance by using text-to-speech software or graphic organizers that can help to increase their self-esteem.

F. MULTISENSORY INSTRUCTIONS:

Multisensory instruction is a technique that offers multiple ways to comprehend information and knowledge by various sensory signals. A study done by Gulati, Kakkar, & Chauhan (2024) concluded that multisensory is an educational approach that helps students in their learning process by enhancing their academic performance in an inclusive setting. The multisensory approach exhibited significant utility in improving the reading capacity of students with dyslexia by providing a more comprehensive and associable way to read (Dr. Fujita, 2024).

G. EXPLICIT INSTRUCTION:

Explicit instruction strategies are a systematic and teacher-led approach, aiming to develop the learning capacity of the children with learning disabilities by focusing on breaking skills into small parts, modelling, and guiding them. Research done by Peltier (2024) demonstrated that explicit instruction can facilitate the academic performance of students with learning disabilities. One of the most effective learning strategies is explicit instruction for teaching students with dyscalculia (Doabler & Fien, 2013).

H. INDIVIDUALISED LEARNING PLAN:

Individualised learning plan serves as a framework that construct a set of activities to align with a diverse academic and developmental needs of each student that facilitates their academic

performance. A study executed by (lockspeiser & Kaul, 2016) suggested that individualised learning plan work as a tool to enhance student's performance, regardless of their diverse background. According to Donaire, Hurtada, & Cagape (2024) by providing structural framework individualised learning plan significantly improve the academic performance for the students with disabilities.

4.METHODOLOGY:

This is a conceptual study that focuses on effective teaching strategies for children with learning disabilities in an inclusive classroom. The research uses a qualitative and non-empirical approach. The study uses the phenomenological method, where data is taken through the direct observational and interview methods of 20 students with specific learning disabilities between 5 to 16 years of age.

5.DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS:

Through prior appointment, school authorities were informed about the objective of the study and permission was taken for data collection. The data was gathered by the case study and interview methods. Through case history researcher is able to identify the students with learning disabilities. 20 students are considered as subject for this research from different schools. Then the data was collected through interview methods. During the interview session teachers and the subjects are encouraged to answers the specific questions related to the research topic.

A total of 20 data were considered for final qualitative analysis. After taking data from the subjects and teachers, it was carefully analysed to pick up the relevant information for the purpose of this research and interpreted the data by calculating the percentage.

6.RESULTS AND FINDINGS:

The main aim of the study is to determine the effective strategies for children learning with disabilities in inclusive classrooms. The major problem with inclusive education is that the children with learning disabilities often fall behind other children in learning and knowledge. Teachers integrate various pedagogical techniques to facilitate the learning process, cognitive development and to enhance student's knowledge. From the present study it has been observed that many students (25%), despite their diverse backgrounds reached their academic targets

through the use of mixed pedagogical approaches used by educators. 20% of the subjects responded well to the multisensory teaching approach compared to 15% who participated in constructivist approach. Co-operative learning frameworks and positive behaviour support account for the facilitation of positive outcomes of 10% and 5% of students respectively. On the other hand, for 5% of the students, differentiated learning program and explicit learning methods are applicable to accelerate their learning. Result suggested that educators try to enhance the learning capacity of the students by using individualised learning plan; however, this applies to only 10% of the student's population. The rest of the 5% of the subjects are applying assistive technology like screen readers and word prediction software as their most favourable learning tools.

7.DISCUSSION:

In the present study it is seen that teachers are using multifaceted strategies to bridge the performance gap between neurodivergent students and their neurotypical peers. Although identifying the effective strategy for students with learning disability is challenging, the results highlight several common techniques that teachers frequently adopt for the inclusive classroom.

Sometimes to achieve academic success instructions must be differentiated to align with specific needs, interest and learning capacities of each student. Differentiated education help to increase the learning capacity by encouraging the students to engage in learning process (Subban, 2006). It's evident that differentiated instruction guides the students to become successful by focusing on specific and diverse needs of the students (Joseph, Thomas , Simonette, & Ramsook, 2013).

A co-operative learning approach is a student- centered approach that help students to accomplish the academic target by interact with each other. Cooperative learning strategy encourages a positive and interactive classroom environment where students can reach their academic goals (Paschal, Nyoni, & Mkulu, 2020). This is one of the favourable pedagogical approaches that help the students to improve learning by sharing knowledge regardless of their diversity in all aspect. (Nzuza & Chitiyo, 2024).

Fostering behaviour by positive reinforcement is another technique to improve performance of the students with learning disabilities. The educators execute the positive behaviour support approach to drive academic growth of the students by embedding proactive intervention in classroom setting (Ali, 2023). By reducing negative behaviour of the students with special needs, positive behaviour support techniques may encourage the academic performance of the students in an inclusive setting (Santosa, Zuhaery, & Iriyani, 2025Edunesia: Jurnal Ilmaiah Pendidikan).

Many students are responded positively in constructivism learning method. As a student-centered approach, constructivism creates a positive and optimal environment that help the students to learn effectively (Sanal & Erdem, 2022). By using the constructivism models such as peer-tutoring, scaffolding educators help the students to perform successfully that may essential for their academic outcomes (Jamir & Jamir, 2024).

Individualised learning plan has a great influence on promoting subjective well-being and enhancing the academic achievement. Multidisciplinary teams collaborate to develop individualised learning plan, that ensuring successful results for students with learning disabilities (Xanthacou & Stroggilos, 2006). An Individualized learning plan helps all students to achieve good academic results, regardless of their individual needs and interest y (Kumar , 2013).

Learning become more effective when students learn through all senses. The multisensory approach promotes students' engagement in learning process by activating all senses than focusing on dual-senses senses (Theresia & Recard, 2021). Multisensory learning approach facilitates the students' academic graph by relating new ideas and knowledge with prior once (Esplendori, Kabayashi, & Puschel, 2022).

Explicit teaching methods enable the teacher to identify the learner's need and implement highly structured, instructional strategies accordingly. By using explicit learning methods students significantly demonstrate higher test scores compared to those following traditional teaching style (Neeman & Amit, 2016). Research done by Vaughn & Fletcher (2021) suggested that explicit learning techniques provide support for the students, especially those with learning disabilities.

Assistive devices provide empower students with learning disabilities to improve their inherent capacities and overcome academic barriers despite individual challenges. By integrating appropriate assistive devices, educators an ensure academic success across diverse learning environment (Dr. Alghamdi, 2025). Assistive devices foster inclusivity by providing equal opportunities and enhancing the academic performance of learners (Aprilia, Suwandayani, & Kuncahyono, 2025).

Integrating diverse pedagogical techniques is one of the most effective and important strategies for accelerating knowledge acquisition of the students with learning disabilities. Blended learning approaches create a positive learning environment by promoting equality that yields better students' outcomes by actively engaging the learners in the learning process despite of their diverse background (Naja & Dr. Hameed, 2024). To manage an inclusive classroom effectively and to accommodate the diversity, teachers should use integrate learning strategies that address the uniqueness and individual requirements of every student (Dr. Begum, et al., 2024).

Teachers use one or a combination of teaching methods to meet the unique needs and interest of every student. By applying this approach educators empower children with specific learning disabilities to develop their individual abilities, that allowing them to progress alongside with their peers and help to achieve their personal goals.

8.CONCLUSION:

These results conclude that inclusive classrooms are defined by students with diverse needs and multifaceted backgrounds. Supporting the neurodivergent learner teachers require to adopt flexible strategies that address every learner's needs and interest. The evidence suggests that integrated teaching methods—which combine various instructional tools are significantly more effective in promoting students' achievement than relying on one specific strategy.

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